

1 **Title:**

2 Impacts of land use change on ecosystem services and implications for human well-being in
3 Spanish drylands

4
5 **Abstract**

6 The arid southeastern Iberian Peninsula is a unique region in which conservation and human
7 development have coexisted and coevolved over many decades. However, conflicts between
8 economic development and conservation have generated increasing concern due to the rapid
9 expansion of greenhouse horticulture and the abandonment of rural and mountainous areas. Human
10 decisions regarding land use management have affected the status of ecosystems and therefore the
11 ecosystem services supply. We identified four land use-land cover changes that summarize the most
12 common management decisions. These include greenhouse horticulture expansion, urban
13 intensification, rural abandonment, and conservation actions, which occur through protected area
14 declarations. This study aims to explore the social relevance of land use-land cover changes on the
15 delivery of eight key services provided by Spanish arid ecosystems as follows: provisioning
16 services related to intensive and traditional agriculture, regulating services associated with water
17 regulation, climate regulation, air quality and erosion control, and cultural services linked to local
18 identity and tourism. Through 402 face-to-face questionnaires, we analyzed the arguments for and
19 against these four land use-land cover types. We also assessed their impact on ecosystem services
20 and the social importance and vulnerability of ecosystem services. We found significant differences
21 in the social perception of the positive and negative impacts of land use types on ecosystem
22 services. The sample population recognized the negative impacts of greenhouse horticulture on
23 regulating services that are, in terms of water regulation, essential for the sustained delivery of final
24 provisioning services related to agricultural activities. Overall, traditional agriculture and tourism
25 are recognized as the most important services. A controversy between the two opposite models of
26 territorial development – urban development and nature conservation – highlights the need to
27 promote new strategies of land management. Finally, we discuss the usefulness of this approach to
28 understand the arguments affecting the promotion of land use-land cover changes and to visualize
29 the ecosystem service trade-offs under different management strategies.

30 **Keywords:** argument analysis, arid, conservation, greenhouse, rural abandonment, urbanization.

31

32 **1. Introduction**

33 Land use-land cover (LULC) changes are a driver of global change that directly affects the status
34 and integrity of ecosystems, and in last term its capacity to supply ecosystem services. LULC
35 changes thus merit special attention for land management and planning due to their potentially
36 negative consequences, creating trade-offs between some ecosystem services (Nelson et al., 2010;
37 Pereira et al., 2012). For instance, the urban intensification that has occurred in recent decades has
38 been accompanied by large increases in resource consumption, habitat fragmentation and
39 biodiversity loss (Foley et al., 2005; Lawler et al., 2014). In other situations, LULC decisions have
40 preserved ecological values and ecosystem services through conservation strategies, including the
41 designation of protected areas (Abram et al., 2014). In this sense, LULC changes affect both habitat
42 characteristics linked to biodiversity and ecosystem services that are vital to the maintenance of
43 human well-being (Foley et al., 2005; Schröter et al., 2005). Often, these decisions create
44 compromises or trade-offs when a given land management strategy enhances the delivery of
45 particular ecosystem services while limiting others (Mouchet et al., 2014). For example, Butler et
46 al. (2011) identified a direct trade-off between food and fiber production versus water quality
47 regulation, and Rodríguez et al. (2006) demonstrated how actions to enhance the supply of food and
48 timber have led to declines in nutrient cycling and flood regulation services. Other authors have
49 identified trade-offs between economic development and the provision of landscape aesthetic value
50 and water supply for human use (Vidal-Legaz et al., 2013).

51

52 In this context, management decisions should promote sustainable landscape strategies in
53 which human needs are satisfied while maintaining the capacity of the ecosystem to preserve key
54 ecosystem services (McShane et al., 2011). In fact, several studies have stated the importance of
55 exploring how land management influences the delivery of ecosystem services as different
56 management strategies can change the relationships among ecosystem services, often creating
57 opportunities to promote or deteriorate services simultaneously (Bennet et al., 2009; Mouchet et al.,
58 2014). In this way, the aim of this study was to explore the arguments that support and oppose the
59 promotion of LULC changes, as well as to assess their impact on a variety of ecosystem services
60 provided by arid Spanish ecosystems. The selected ecosystem services included food production
61 from traditional agricultural methods, food production from intensive agricultural methods, air
62 quality, climate regulation, water regulation, erosion control, tourism and local identity.

63

64 In the arid ecosystems of the Mediterranean region of southeastern Spain, the consequences
65 of LULC changes on the capacity of ecosystems to provide services are especially important due to
66 the ecological vulnerability and high biodiversity of these ecosystems (Palutikof et al., 1996; Sala et
67 al., 2000; Lázaro et al., 2001; Spanish NEA, 2014). This area is the driest region in continental
68 Europe (García-Latorre et al., 2001; Armas et al., 2011) and has experienced one of the most
69 dramatic and significant LULC transformations in all Europe, with enormous economic and socio-
70 cultural consequences (Aznar-Sánchez et al., 2011; Muñoz-Rojas et al., 2011). It has one of the
71 highest population growth rates in Spain, where immigrants account for 22% of the total population.
72 It also has a birth rate above the Spanish average (Wolosin, 2008; INE, 2011). Since 1960, land-
73 planning strategies to promote socio-economic development in this area caused four policy-based
74 main LULC changes: (1) a rapid transition toward intensive greenhouse horticulture in coastal areas
75 (representing 3.15% of the study area surface) (UNEP, 2005; Aznar-Sánchez et al., 2011) promoted
76 by the National Institute of Rural Development and Colonization (Royal legislative decree
77 24/06/41); (2) urban expansion associated with population growth produced by agriculture
78 intensification and massive tourism along the coastline (2.65% of the study area surface) promoted
79 by the Andalusian law 7/2002 in Urban Planning; (3) rural abandonment produced by the exodus of
80 people toward urban areas along the coast (44.52% of the study area surface), which is currently
81 combated by the Spanish law 45/2007 on Rural Development; and (4) the declaration of the
82 protected area networks with the aim of conserving the unique ecological value of this territory
83 (20% of the study area surface), as for example *Sierra Nevada National Park* (Spanish law 3/1999)
84 or the *Cabo de Gata Natural Park* (Andalusian legislative decree 314/1987) (Figure 1). Based on
85 these land transformations, particularly related to agriculture intensification, this period was
86 described as “the Almería miracle” in response to the conversion of the driest regions in Europe into
87 one of the most economically prosperous areas in the country due to the proliferation of greenhouse
88 horticulture (Mota et al., 1996).

89
90 In the face of these land use transformation, this study explores the arguments supporting
91 and against these LULC changes, their links with components of human well-being and the drivers
92 of change, and their impacts on ecosystem services supply. More specifically, to understand the
93 factors behind the promotion of LULC changes in the study area, we (1) identified the arguments
94 for and against the promotion of each LULC type, (2) analyzed the social perception of the impacts
95 of LULC on eight ecosystem services provided by the region, and (3) explored the social
96 importance and perceived vulnerability of ecosystem services. Our research contributes to an

97 improved understanding of the relationships between LULC transformation and human well-being
98 and the interaction between LULC changes and ecosystem services. Finally, we discuss how the
99 results support specific targets of existing European policies in terms of the legal framework and
100 strategies to enhance biodiversity (Spanish law 42/2007 on Natural Heritage and Biodiversity) and
101 rural development (Law 45/2007 on Rural Development), and how they can contribute to promote
102 new sustainable land management strategies.

103

104 **2. Study area: Arid ecosystems of the Iberian Peninsula and the occurring LULC changes**

105

106 The study area is located predominantly in the Almería province and, to a lesser extent, in
107 the Granada province, covering approximately 1,220.711 ha (Figure 1). The mean annual
108 temperature in the region varies from 12 to 18°C, and the annual precipitation is below 350
109 mm/year in most of this territory (Armas et al., 2011). This region is distinguished by the presence
110 of arid landscapes and diverse land use types.

111

112 #Fig. 1 approximately here#

113

114 Over the last 50 years, this arid region has experienced one of the largest LULC changes in
115 the territory, which has been driven by the introduction of intensive greenhouse agricultural
116 practices. Before 1960, this area was described as one of the poorest provinces in Spain (Sánchez-
117 Picón et al., 2011). Historically, the conditions for human occupancy have been unfavorable,
118 marked by scarce rainfall, rough land and frequent strong winds (Wolosin, 2008). The development
119 model was fundamentally limited by water scarcity, and it was dedicated to subsistence agriculture
120 characterized by dry farming with low yields. It was not until 1970 that this socio-economic model
121 changed, led by the development of intensive agriculture, the tourism sector and the construction
122 industry (CAMP, 2013). From 1982 to 2003, this region developed into the major producer of
123 vegetables for Spain and other European Union countries. The region now holds the largest
124 concentration of greenhouses in the world (approx. 26,750 ha) and is known as *El Poniente* (UNEP,
125 2005) and *The Plastic Sea* of Almería (Aznar-Sánchez et al., 2011) (Figure 2A-B). The rapid
126 development of this sector was fueled through the use of groundwater (and later desalinated sea
127 water), the introduction of innovative technologies (such as biological control), the high number of
128 sunny hours and the absence of a true thermal winter (CAMP, 2013).

129

130 As a result of the promotion of agricultural intensification, the area experienced a population
131 boom coupled with the development of urban areas. On the one hand, the increasing population led
132 to a rise in urban intensification in littoral areas and converted the Almería province into one of
133 Spain's most transformed provinces. On the other hand, this urban intensification, coupled with the
134 lack of employment in rural areas and the low profits from the traditional agriculture, provoked the
135 migration of people from rural areas to urban areas in search for better opportunities. Subsequently,
136 this promoted the depopulation of rural areas and the resulting abandonment of traditional
137 agriculture (EEA, 2010; Fischer et al., 2012; Iniesta-Arandia et al., 2015), causing a subsequent loss
138 of traditional crops (Appendix A).

139

140

#Fig. 2 approximately here#

141

142 Concurrent with these extensive land transformations, there has been a simultaneous effort
143 to protect natural areas with unique biodiversity (Hose, 2007). As a result, 30 protected areas have
144 been declared in last three decades, converting the percentage of conserved land surface from 4% to
145 20%. Examples of this conservation effort include the declaration of *Cabo de Gata Natural Park* in
146 1987 and the *Sierra Nevada National Park* in 1999. Currently, the percentage of protected areas
147 within the study area is above both the average for Andalusia region (19.86%) and Spain (12.85%
148 of surface protected).

149

150 **3. Methods**

151

152 *3.1. Data sampling and questionnaire design*

153

154 From February to April 2012, we conducted face-to-face questionnaires with local residents.
155 Overall, 402 valid questionnaires were completed and used in this study (Figure 1). Social sampling
156 was conducted at 26 different sampling sites, and the population sampled was randomly selected.
157 Sampling covered a wide range of stakeholder backgrounds, involving residents working in the
158 primary sector, such as farmers (both from greenhouses and traditional practices), housewives,
159 workers in the tertiary sector, and workers in public administration. The questionnaires collected
160 information regarding (1) the arguments for and against of LULC types, (2) the perceived impact of
161 LULC types on ecosystem services, (3) the perceived importance and vulnerability (increase, stable
162 or decrease) of ecosystem services, and (4) the socio-demographic information of area residents.

163

164 We asked respondents to provide arguments for and against each LULC type using panels
165 illustrating the four LULC types to facilitate their understanding (see Appendix A; REDIAM,
166 2007). We made no effort to force people to provide arguments; respondents were given the option
167 to not provide an argument if they did not recognize any (Sherren and Verstraten, 2013). This was
168 conducted to consider only the arguments for which the respondents had a formed an opinion of the
169 topic. From the narratives and an analysis of the words in the description provided by the
170 respondents, we identified several main topics. We then developed initial categories for these topics
171 and grouped similar arguments by each LULC type identifying the most representative categories.
172 Based on Palomo et al. (2013) and using the conceptual framework of the Millennium Ecosystem
173 Assessment (MA, 2005) and the Spanish National Ecosystem Assessment (Spanish NEA, 2014), we
174 related the arguments to direct drivers of global change (any factor that directly alters ecosystems,
175 such as land use change, climatic change, pollution, invasive alien species, biogeochemical cycles
176 changes and overexploitation), to indirect drivers of change (such as the demographic, economic,
177 socio-political, science and technology or social factors and processes that act in a more diffuse way
178 by altering ecosystems), and to components of human well-being (the basic material for a good life,
179 health, good social relations, security and freedom of choice and action). Arguments were linked to
180 drivers of change and to components of human well-being if a predominant and explicit relationship
181 was identified. Positive arguments were linked to indirect drivers and human well-being
182 components. For instance, the creation of economic development was linked to economic progress
183 as an indirect driver and to the production of basic material for a good life as a human well-being
184 component (Table 1). However, negative arguments were linked to indirect drivers, components of
185 human well-being, but also to direct drivers of change which act as pressures and negative effects.
186 For example, the negative argument of excessive land occupation attached to greenhouse
187 horticulture was linked to the direct driver of change of land use.

188

189 Secondly, we explored how respondents interpreted the impact of LULC (either positive or
190 negative) on the ecosystem services. We used eight previously identified key ecosystem services
191 according to their relevance in relation to LULC changes and their ecological characteristics as they
192 related to arid conditions (Castro et al., 2011; García-Llorente et al., 2012a; Castro et al., 2014;
193 Quintas-Soriano et al., 2014). The selected ecosystem services were food production from
194 traditional agriculture, food production from intensive agriculture, air quality, climate regulation,

195 water regulation, erosion control, tourism and local identity (see Appendix B for a full description
196 of the ecosystem services).

197

198 Finally, the respondents were asked to choose two ecosystem services that were positively
199 impacted by each LULC type and two that were negatively impacted. In total, the respondents
200 chose a maximum of 4 ecosystem services that were impacted for each LULC. Additionally, the
201 respondents assigned an intensity score for each impact ranging from 1 (minimum intensity) to 10
202 (maximum intensity). Unselected ecosystem services were rated as neutral. We then used spider
203 diagrams to compare the positive and negative impacts of each LULC type on the ecosystem
204 services supply. Differences between the perceived impacts of the LULC on ecosystem services
205 were explored using a non-parametric Kruskal–Wallis statistical test. Finally, the respondents were
206 asked to indicate the relative importance and perceived trend (decrease, increase or no change) of
207 each ecosystem service. To do this, they were asked to select from the panel the four ecosystem
208 services most important to them (Appendix B). They then indicated the trend of each ecosystem
209 service over the past 10 years. All statistical analyses were performed using the software package
210 XLSTAT 2010.

211

212 **4. Results**

213

214 The average age of the respondents was 40.88 years, and there was an almost even
215 distribution between the male and female respondents (53.98% male and 46.02% female). The
216 sample included respondents working in the agricultural industry, the public administration sector
217 and housewives among others. Most of the respondents had reached professional or university-level
218 education (34.08% and 33.08%, respectively), and 42.79% of respondents had a monthly income
219 under 900€. The respondents presented an active interest in nature with respect to recycling habits
220 (52.49% of the respondents reported that they always or almost always recycle) and an interest in
221 the protected areas, which they frequently reported visiting within the previous year.

222

223 *4.1. Arguments for and against each LULC*

224

225 Protected areas were the LULC type that garnered the most social support (71.64% of the
226 respondents expressed positive arguments for this LULC), followed by greenhouse horticulture
227 (69.15%), urban intensification (55.22%), and rural abandonment (24.88%). The LULC urban

228 intensification had the greatest number of arguments against it (74.88% of the respondents
229 expressed negative arguments for this LULC), followed by greenhouse horticulture (69.67%), rural
230 abandonment (35.91%) and protected areas (31.84%). Table 1 summarizes the variety of arguments
231 for and against each LULC, as well as the direct and indirect drivers identified and the related
232 components of human well-being.

233

234 #Table 1 approximately here#

235

236 The positive arguments for greenhouse horticulture were mostly related to employment and
237 economy. For example, respondents considered this agricultural practice important for the
238 *promotion of employment and lifestyle* (42.09%) and for the *creation of economic development*
239 (28.06%). Some respondents related greenhouse horticulture to the quality and abundance of food,
240 using positive arguments such as *increasing farming productivity* (12.23%) and *obtaining products*
241 *out of season* (9.71%). These arguments are related to the components of human well-being of basic
242 material for a good life (e.g., acquiring shelter and food) and security, which are promoted by
243 economic development (an indirect driver of change; Table 1). However, other respondents were of
244 the opinion that this greenhouse horticulture was related primarily to a negative environmental
245 impact in the form of *pollution* (both the pollution from burning agricultural plastics and the
246 chemical contamination of soil and water from pesticides; 30.30%), *aesthetic impact* (16.21%),
247 *general ecological impact* (9.85%) and *soil erosion* (4.55%). These negative arguments were mainly
248 related to the direct driver of land use change and their impact on the environment; they were linked
249 to the health component of human well-being. Respondents also visualized negative arguments
250 associated to demographic and socio-political factors, such as the *social inequality and worker*
251 *overexploitation* that occur in the area (6.06%).

252

253 Respondents identified similar positive arguments for urban intensification linked to
254 economic factors, such as its contribution to the *promotion of employment* (42.79%), *creation of*
255 *housing* (17.57%), *increasing tourism* (6.31%) and *increasing population* (5.41%). Other arguments
256 mentioned this in a general way (referencing the *creation of economic development*, with 13.96% of
257 the respondents expressing positive arguments for this LULC, or the *promotion of human well-*
258 *being* with 9.46% of the respondents using this argument), linked to the basic material for a good
259 life and security as components of human well-being (Table 1). However, most of the respondents
260 considered economic and socio-political drivers to be the main factors responsible for *corruption*

261 *and speculation* in the political arena (16.94%), *uncontrolled urban expansion and housing*
262 *oversupply* (45.85%), and *overpriced housing* (4.65%) (Table 1). These drivers were mainly related
263 to environmental problems produced by urban intensification in terms of *ecological impact*
264 (11.30%), *soil loss* (3.32%) and *aesthetic impact* (4.98%).

265
266 Positive arguments associated with rural abandonment were related to the search for
267 improved well-being in other areas (but not to the positive aspects of rural abandonment itself).
268 These were mainly the *search for job opportunities* (34%) and *life quality improvements* (27%).
269 These arguments seemed to be driven by indirect demographic and economic drivers and mostly
270 referred to the human security and freedom of choice and action as components of human well-
271 being. Positive arguments were also connected to the *restoration of natural environment* (13%) due
272 to the migration of the local population. On the contrary, negative arguments related to this LULC
273 included references to *rural depopulation* (16.17%) linked to the *loss of local identity and local*
274 *traditional knowledge* (41.32%) and the loss of traditional crops or *crop abandonment* (11.98%)
275 (Table 1). These negative arguments were connected to the indirect demographic driver of change.

276
277 Finally, the importance of nature conservation to the respondents was evidenced by the
278 positive and conservational arguments found according to this LULC type (e.g., *environment*
279 *conservation and biodiversity protection*; 64.93%). In addition, the respondents linked protected
280 areas with the *promotion of human well-being and health* (9.38%) and with the economic benefits
281 of tourism (6.94%). These positive arguments were linked to the components of human well-being
282 of basic material for a good life and health (Table 1). In contrast, restrictive protection within these
283 areas included negative arguments that were interpreted in terms of limiting human activity (e.g.,
284 the *excessive legislation and banning* (35.94%) and the *limitation of development and activities*
285 (14.06%)) and were related to their effects on the freedom of choice and action of human well-
286 being. These negative arguments are connected to socio-political and economic drivers of change.

287 288 4.2. Perceived impacts of LULC on ecosystem services

289
290 We found significant differences among the perceived impacts of all LULC on the eight
291 ecosystem services (Table 2). Respondents perceived greenhouse horticulture impacting all
292 ecosystem services negatively, with the exception of intensive agriculture service, which was

293 impacted positively. In particular, water regulation and climate regulation were the services
294 perceived as most negatively impacted (Figure 3).

295
296 #Table 2 approximately here#

297
298 Similarly, respondents recognized the negative impact of urban intensification on regulating
299 services, such as climate regulation, air quality, water regulation and erosion control, and on
300 traditional agriculture. In fact, urban intensification was the perceived LULC that affected erosion
301 control most negatively (Table 2; Figure 3) but had the highest positive impact on tourism.

302
303 #Fig. 3 approximately here#

304
305 Rural abandonment was linked to the maintenance of ecological processes, positively
306 impacting regulating services but also negatively impacting traditional agricultural practices. We
307 found significant differences showing that rural abandonment was the LULC with the most negative
308 impact on traditional agriculture and local identity (see Table 2). Moreover, respondents perceived
309 negative impacts on cultural services and on erosion control associated with the abandonment of
310 agricultural traditional practices that are used for soil conservation, such as terracing (Figure 3).

311
312 Conversely, protected areas were perceived as providers of regulating services, especially air
313 quality, climate regulation and erosion control. However, protected areas were also perceived as a
314 barrier to provisioning services delivery, particularly intensive agriculture, due to the restrictions of
315 extractive uses within these areas in terms of agricultural products (see Table 2).

316 317 *4.3. Preferences and perceived trend of ecosystem services*

318
319 Tourism (73.13% of respondents selected it as important), traditional agriculture (64.43%)
320 and air quality (58.96%) were considered to be the most relevant services. Meanwhile, erosion
321 control received the lowest recognition (33.58%); followed by intensive agriculture (36.58%)
322 (Figure 4A). Other ecosystem services had average values of importance.

323
324 #Fig. 4 approximately here#

325

326 Many of the respondents perceived that regulating services (air quality, climate regulation,
327 water regulation and erosion control) had decreased in the last decade, affecting the capacity of arid
328 systems to provide these services, whereas cultural services (tourism and local identity) were
329 perceived as having a positive trend. Regarding provisioning services, traditional agriculture was
330 perceived mainly as decreasing, whereas intensive agriculture was perceived as increasing (Figure
331 4B). In this way, tourism was a socially relevant service experiencing an increase in the area.
332 However, other socially relevant services, such as traditional agriculture and water regulation, were
333 in a vulnerable state, perceived as decreasing in the last years.

334

335 **5. Discussion**

336

337 Currently the links between ecosystem services and land use changes are emerging as a way
338 to better understand the dynamics of coupled human and natural systems (Fu et al., 2015). Most of
339 the previous research has focused principally on quantifying biophysical changes in ecosystem
340 services supply under different land use scenarios (e.g., Muñoz-Rojas et al., 2011; Felipe-Lucia et
341 al., 2014; Lawler et al., 2014; Queiroz et al., 2015). However, a current challenge involves
342 analyzing the links between ecosystem services supply and both drivers of change and human well-
343 being (Pereira et al., 2005). This study takes a step forward in the analysis of these relationships by
344 exploring (1) the links between specific LULC types and ecosystem services (e.g., the relationship
345 between protected areas and regulating services) and (2) social arguments behind the changes in
346 land use and their implications for human well-being (e.g., relationship between greenhouse
347 horticulture and the creation of employment) (Figure 5). Linking these two inputs allows us to
348 visualize more explicitly the potential trade-offs that practitioners must take into account in order to
349 better understand the complexity behind the promotion of diverse land management policies.
350 Recognizing this complexity is key to understanding not just the ecological and social implications
351 of different land-based policies, but also to providing evidences of synergies and mismatches
352 between coupled human and natural systems (Castro et al., 2016).

353

354 At the same time, taking into account the social perspectives of local residents can lead to
355 higher quality and more reliable environmental decision making (Davies et al., 2015). Future
356 management policies should link human well-being with the ecosystem services enhancement,
357 taking into account social perspectives to obtain more adaptive policies. In this way, based on the
358 decisions made on LULC and their impact on the ecosystem services, it is essential to manage

359 ecosystems and to create future economies that foster both sustainable ecosystem services supply
360 use and the promotion of human well-being (Reyers et al., 2009).

361

362 5.1. Understanding arguments on LULC changes

363

364 In the Mediterranean region, two contrasting trends in LULC changes have been identified
365 over the last several decades (Ruiz-Benito et al., 2010). First, industrial development, which is an
366 intensification of agricultural practices and urban expansion, is reshaping the landscape (e.g.,
367 Gulinck et al., 2001; Antrop, 2004). Second, a concurrent increase in the abandonment of rural
368 areas has led to a decrease in traditional agricultural practices. Both processes feature heavily in the
369 case study (García-Llorente et al., 2012b; Stellmes et al., 2013) and are identified as the key drivers
370 of global change (Spanish NEA, 2014).

371

372 One of the most recognizable land transformations on a global scale is the high
373 concentration of greenhouse horticulture located in the study area (Aznar-Sánchez et al., 2011;
374 Aguilar et al., 2015). This area has become the largest producer of vegetables at the European level,
375 becoming the basis of the regional economy and increasing the local standard of living (Mota et al.,
376 1996). This land transformation is socially supported by its links with improvements in quality of
377 life and economic development (Figure 2A-B; Figure 5). Respondents linked the economic profits
378 provided by greenhouse horticulture with human development as this economic driver provides
379 stability and security and the basic material for a good life through factors such as income security,
380 tranquility and safety (Figure 5). However, the respondents also reported several perceived negative
381 impacts of greenhouse horticulture on nature, such as *pollution*, *ecological impact* and *aesthetic*
382 *impact*, as shown in previous studies (Zalidis et al., 2002; Dale and Polasky, 2007; Muñoz et al.,
383 2008; García-Llorente et al., 2012b). This was consistent with findings of Pereira et al. (2005), who
384 reported that respondents involved in agricultural landscapes considered the quality of food to be
385 lower due to the use of chemicals and pesticides. We also observed a similar number of positive and
386 negative arguments (68.17% versus 66.88%, respectively) describing the controversy and
387 complexity of greenhouse horticulture and the challenge of making this LULC type more
388 sustainable. As García-Llorente et al. (2015) state, changing the focus of intensive agriculture from
389 the maximization of food production to the production of food combined with other ecosystem
390 services could help to increase social-ecological resilience (Gordon et al., 2010) and to promote the

391 viability of rural areas through the diversification of the services provided (Power et al., 2010; Di
392 Iacovo et al., 2014).

393

394

#Fig. 5 approximately here#

395

396 The economic transformation promoted that the Almería province as became into one of the
397 most transformed regions in all Spain in terms of urban expansion and construction. Indeed, this
398 region has the largest number of housing units built in Spain (Gonzalez and Ortega, 2009). Urban
399 expansion has fostered an explosion of *sun and beach tourism* at the southwest of the study area (a
400 sort of tourism that takes place on coastlines, where tourists usually sun bathe during the day),
401 where there is a lack of environmental regulation which has been promoted by short-term policies
402 of urban development (Vivas-Puig, 2007). Similar trends have been found in other Spanish regions,
403 including the mountainous regions of Madrid (Hewitt and Escobar, 2011) and the coastal areas of
404 Barcelona (Dupras et al., 2015). Arguments supporting urban expansion note that people clearly
405 perceive the economic benefits associated with construction and urban intensification (Martín-
406 García, 2007), specifically the increase in job opportunities in the construction sector (see Table 1).
407 However, there is a growing negative perception toward urban intensification and the speculative
408 property bubble linked with corruption and speculation issues in the policy arena (for example, see
409 arguments regarding *uncontrolled urban expansion and housing oversupply, corruption and*
410 *speculation and ecological impact*). This issue has been widely documented in Spain in previous
411 studies (Romero et al., 2012; García-Quesada et al., 2015), in which people reported being very
412 concerned about illegal practices in the rezoning of lands favorable to construction. This is likely
413 why the respondents perceived political corruption as an important problem associated with urban
414 development in Spain (Jiménez et al., 2014; Villoria et al., 2014), with economic and socio-political
415 indirect drivers behind this LULC intensification. An example of this are the complaints made in
416 the study area over the last 15 years by non-governmental environmental organizations, such as
417 Greenpeace, denouncing the construction of the hotel *El Algarrobico*, which was built within the
418 boundaries of *Cabo de Gata Natural Park* (see Figure 1 and Figure 2C) (Garrido Cumbreira and
419 López-Lara, 2010). This hotel exemplifies the conflicting interpretation of the environmental
420 Andalusian Law 2/1989 from different administrative scales and social sectors: the regional
421 government's Network of Protected Areas declared this area to be a Natural Park, thus restricting
422 any human development, whereas the economic need of the local municipalities often supersedes

423 such environmental protection and is used to justify intensive development at the expense of
424 ecosystem integrity.

425

426 Our results show a general consensus regarding the negative opinions of the effects of rural
427 abandonment on ecosystems. This was shown by the type and number of arguments (41.50%
428 against, versus 24.51% in favor) related to the importance of cultural and traditional values of rural
429 lands. In previous studies, rural abandonment has been visualized as a means of recovering natural
430 environments and as an opportunity to re-wild abandoned areas (Navarro and Pereira, 2012).
431 However, in the Mediterranean, rural abandonment is more often related to the loss of multi-
432 functionality and a less diverse flow of ecosystem services, such as the loss of local ecological
433 knowledge, erosion control and water regulation (Altieri and Toledo, 2005; Blondel et al., 2010;
434 Arnaez et al., 2011; García-Llorente et al., 2012b; Iniesta-Arandia et al., 2015). Today, one of the
435 major problems facing the Mediterranean region is widespread land abandonment (Weissteiner et
436 al., 2011), which is due to a dwindling and aging rural population, resulting in fewer job
437 opportunities and the continuous emigration of young people from this area (Spanish NEA, 2014).
438 All of these processes have reinforced the abandonment trend, resulting in the disappearance of the
439 rural community and its associated traditional knowledge and cultural heritage, leading to the
440 overall impoverishment of the affected rural areas (Pereira et al., 2005).

441

442 Despite the LULC changes, this region has one of the highest proportions of protected areas
443 as 22% of the land is protected compared with 19.86% of the land in the Andalusia region and
444 12.85% of the land in Spain overall. This highlights the controversy existing in this area between
445 two opposite models of territorial development; whereas there is massive *sun and beach tourism*
446 based on urban intensification, nature conservation represents the dominant land use in the
447 southeastern portion of the study area (Figure 1). One of the protected areas, the *Cabo de Gata*
448 *Natural Park*, represents the major tourism attraction in the region, with approximately 300,000
449 visits in 2009 (Muñoz-Flores, 2011). We identified this point to be a conceptualization of human
450 development based on the creation of protected areas to both conserve the environment and to
451 promote related economic activities, such as ecotourism. Positive arguments supporting protected
452 areas demonstrate that respondents identify these areas in terms of enjoying healthy environments
453 and nature conservation, leading to *increasing tourism* (Table 1). Whereas in the past, protected
454 areas were mainly designed for conserving scenic beauty and wildlife and ban human activities
455 (Pyke, 2007), recent studies show a different tendency in the way the public perceives protected

456 areas and how the incorporation of ecosystem services could overcome conservation challenges, not
457 just in protected land, but also in surrounding landscapes, making conservation actions more
458 publicly accepted (Armsworth et al., 2007; Palomo et al., 2014a; Castro et al., 2015). However,
459 although the surface of protected areas have increased in recent years, ecosystems continue to be
460 fragmented and degraded (Watson et al., 2014), and the rate of biodiversity loss continues to
461 increase (Pereira et al., 2010). This demonstrates the challenge of managing protected areas as
462 provider of human wellbeing (Castro et al., 2015), in addition to managing these areas for
463 biodiversity conservation. An example of this controversy between development and conservation
464 is the *Punta Entinas-Sabinar Natural Reserve*, which is located within the study area (Figure 1;
465 Figure 2D). According to the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN), this area is
466 the most restricted for human use and contains the most well-conserved dune systems in the Iberian
467 Peninsula. However, as a result of subsequent local policies, that promoted greenhouse horticulture
468 and urban development in the surrounding areas, the general public does not perceive the utilitarian
469 value of this protected land and instead it is generally considered as a barrier for economic
470 development (Kuriyan, 2002; Allendorf, 2007). It could be related with the classical island
471 management model followed in protected areas till the 80' where the management of protected
472 areas were not integrated in the territory (Palomo et al. 2014b).

473
474 As Pereira et al. (2005) suggested, we believe that developing responses that increase both
475 ecosystem service preservation and human well-being are key to understanding the link among
476 local well-being, ecosystem services trends and drivers of change. Accordingly, to produce
477 effective management, the indirect drivers, such as demographic, economic, socio-political, and
478 cultural factors, merit additional study (Carpenter et al., 2006).

479 480 *5.2. Social perceptions of ecosystem services: impacts, importance and trends*

481
482 The analysis of social perceptions has emerged as a first step in the incorporation of social
483 perspectives and stakeholder engagement in environmental management decisions (López-
484 Rodríguez et al., 2015). In fact, social preferences toward ecosystem services are a widely-studied
485 topic (e.g., Castro et al., 2011; García-Llorente et al., 2012a,b; Martín-López et al., 2012). However,
486 to date, the analysis of perceptions has not been linked to LULC types. Results can provide useful
487 information for understanding the complexity of human decisions and the influence of the various
488 LULCs on the deterioration or conservation of ecosystem services. The analyzed social perceptions

489 revealed important trade-offs in the land management, such as the importance placed on traditional
490 agriculture, which is considered to be the second most important ecosystem service (Pereira et al.,
491 2005; García-Llorente et al., 2012a) but is also perceived to have the largest decreasing trend. This
492 decreasing trend is supported by the current management dynamics of the territory, which promotes
493 an increase in intensive agriculture, whereas traditional practices are lost (Weissteiner et al., 2011;
494 Subirós et al., 2015). Interestingly, intensive agriculture is perceived to be a less important
495 ecosystem service but exhibits a significant increasing trend. Although the population has a high
496 level of awareness regarding the ecological impact of greenhouses, the perception that it is less
497 important could indicate that intensive agriculture is not regarded as an ecosystem service but rather
498 as a benefit of the large amount of human, social and built capital required for its delivery (labor,
499 knowledge, technology, etc.) (Costanza et al., 2014), which comprise the relatively lower
500 contributions of ecosystems, with a lesser dependence on maintaining the ecological processes and
501 structures. Indeed, the social preference toward traditional agriculture rather than intensive
502 agriculture shows the greatest discrepancies in the perceived importance of services between both
503 types. In this way, we can differentiate between the following two agricultural models: (1) a
504 commodity based on the production and sales, with a predominance of markets (horticulture
505 agriculture) (Aznar-Sánchez et al., 2011), and (2) an agricultural system that is understood to be a
506 lifestyle coupled with ecosystem integrity that prioritizes the maintenance of traditional practices,
507 such as terracing and the use of water ditches, to effectively promote regulating services and
508 landscape multifunctionality (Iniesta-Arandia et al., 2015).

509
510 The general public recognizes the importance of regulating services but perceives a severe
511 impact and degradation following greenhouse horticulture and urban intensification. This could be
512 explained by the fully invasive character of greenhouse horticulture, which negatively affects key
513 ecological processes, such as water and climate regulation. Tourism is clearly negatively impacted
514 by greenhouse horticulture and rural abandonment. In the case of greenhouses, the decrease in
515 tourism is due to the negative visual impact that it has on the landscape, making views of the region
516 less attractive (García-Llorente et al., 2012b). The explanation for the negative impact of rural
517 abandonment is likely related to the general impoverishment of rural areas. Despite the negative
518 impact on tourism, the respondents considered it to be the most important ecosystem service, with
519 the most positive trend. This result is consistent with findings of Martín-López et al. (2012) and is
520 most likely linked to the role of protected areas in the economy of the study area because it is one of
521 the main economic engines after greenhouse horticulture. Moreover, local identity is favored by all

522 LULC types, except rural abandonment. This is clearly because the consequences of rural
523 abandonment include the impoverishment of the area (with respective consequences for economic
524 power, labor force and infrastructure), a decrease of rural populations, and a relative increase in the
525 percentage of elderly inhabitants in the population (Weissteiner et al., 2011). All of this means that
526 local identity service is not considered to be important and often goes unnoticed. According to
527 Subirós et al. (2015), depopulation also leads to a loss of cultural heritage, not only due to the
528 abandonment of traditional farmhouses (and, therefore, the loss of these architectural values) but
529 also due to the disappearance of traditional economic activities linked to farmhouses.

530

531 *5.3. Moving forward to policy implications and recommendations for European and Spanish* 532 *policies and management of ecosystem services*

533

534 Despite the growing interest in ecosystem services across global science and policy arenas,
535 the application of ecosystem services analysis to management decisions remains unclear, and much
536 of the existing literature does not clarify how the information gathered could be used to inform land
537 policy decisions (Laurans et al., 2013). Recent studies make advances in clarifying how ecosystem
538 service assessments could inform environmental decisions (Carpenter et al., 2009; Schouten et al.,
539 2012; Martinez-Harms et al., 2015), but there are still few studies that provide explicit examples of
540 policy applications. With the aim of identifying implications and recommendations in existing
541 environmental policies, we present how our findings can be integrated in targets or priorities of two
542 European and Spanish policies: on one side the Strategic Plan for Biodiversity 2011–2020 and the
543 Aichi Targets Natural and the Heritage and Biodiversity Spanish Strategic Program (Spanish law
544 42/2007 on Natural Heritage and Biodiversity); and on the other side the EU’s Rural Development
545 Policy and the National Rural Development Programme for Spain (Law 45/2007 on Rural
546 Development) (Table 3).

547

548 #Table 3 approximately here#

549

550 Following the European legislation, by 2020, ecosystems and their services should be
551 maintained and enhanced by establishing green infrastructure and restoring at least 15% of
552 degraded ecosystems (Secretariat of the Convention on Biological Diversity, 2010). In this regard,
553 ecosystem services assessments could be directly implemented in terms of landscape planning
554 instruments to prevent degradation of rural areas characterized by multifunctional agriculture by

555 enhancing its capacity to supply ecosystem services and be designated as high nature value
556 farmland areas¹ (dealing with Target 2 of the European Level; Table 3).

557 In relation to the Spanish national goal 1 (“*obtain the best knowledge for the conservation*
558 *and sustainable use of biodiversity and ecosystem services*”), this study contributes by improving
559 the knowledge on the social perception of the key ecosystem services provided by arid systems and
560 their vulnerability based on different land management decisions and to goal 5 (“*establish as a*
561 *priority element the promotion of responsibility, social participation and social involvement*”) by
562 exploring the diverse knowledge of different stakeholders such as local residents, which have been
563 identified as essential for the successful incorporation of ecosystem services into conservation
564 actions (Martinez-Harms et al., 2015; Castro et al., 2016). This study includes the voice of local
565 communities, so it may serve as a starting point for engaging the general public through public
566 participation and later awareness-raising campaigns. For instance, arguments and perceived
567 negative impacts placed on tourism by rural abandonment indicate directions on how future policies
568 must integrate tourism and conservation actions of rural areas and multifunctional landscapes. In the
569 same way, arguments against protected areas (such as *the excessive legislation and banning and*
570 *limitations of human development*; see Table 1) must be understood as a gap in connecting the
571 services provided by protected areas and human well-being maintenance. Our study shows how the
572 loss of local environmental knowledge is overall identified as a priority for local communities. This
573 result supports the creation of an inventory of traditional knowledge, such as the one recently
574 conducted in Spain (Pardo de Santayana et al., 2014). Also, to preserve and maintain cultural
575 heritage associated to Spanish drylands, we suggest that these results can help the promotion of the
576 collection of memory of the traditional ecological knowledge, acknowledging them as an important
577 part of their cultural heritage at the regional level.

578

579 Secondly, one of the most relevant priorities of the EU’s Rural Development Policy program
580 is “*restoring, preserving and enhancing ecosystems related to agriculture and forestry*” (Priority 4;
581 Table 3). At the Spanish level, the National Rural Development Program establishes as a priority
582 4A “*restoring, preserving and enhancing biodiversity, agricultural systems of high natural value*
583 *and the state of European landscapes*” (European Commission, 2015). Regarding this, the
584 importance identified of rural areas and the social concern of the loss of traditional agriculture
585 (Table 1), considered as one of the most important ecosystem service, can be used for putting in

¹ High nature value farming describes farming systems in Europe of greatest biodiversity value which are inherently valuable for biodiversity and forms a living cultural and natural heritage (Keenleyside et al., 2014).

586 value and revitalizing these areas. On the other side, priority 6B of the National Rural Development
587 Programme is to “*promote the enhancement of natural and cultural heritage as a factor of*
588 *sustainable development*” (Table 3). We suggest that this research can promote participatory
589 process to co-design public policies through the incorporation of multi-stakeholder governance
590 focused on local communities that promote the restoring of agricultural systems and the
591 enhancement of natural and cultural heritage.

592

593 **Conclusions**

594

595 In this study, we undertook an analysis of the positive and negative arguments perceived
596 regarding LULC changes. Specifically, we explored the arguments in conflicts related to the LULC
597 planning strategies that occurred in Spanish arid ecosystems and the social relevance of LULC
598 changes on the delivery of key ecosystem services. The impact of land management decisions on
599 the ecosystem services were analyzed, highlighting the difficulty in facing the binomial relationship
600 between development and conservation. Overall, the respondents were aware of the important
601 impacts and trade-offs related to the LULC changes that occurred but prioritized their well-being
602 based on economic arguments. We believe it is critical to pay attention to societal perceptions
603 driving management decisions because these allow us to explore the relationships between LULC
604 changes and available ecosystem services. Moreover, the controversy existing in this area between
605 two opposite models of territorial development emphasizes the need to promote new strategies for
606 land management. Therefore, analyzing the arguments underlying the specific LULC strategies can
607 help us to adopt specific policies to improve upon current decision-making strategies and include
608 ecosystem services in land decisions and management.

609

610

611 **Acknowledgements**

612 We thank all of the people who kindly responded to our questionnaire. We appreciate the valuable
613 English editing of B. Tweedy. Funding for the development of this research was provided by the
614 Andalusian Center for the Assessment of Global Change (CAESCG) (GLOCHARID project). The
615 Oklahoma Biological Survey and the South Central Climate Science Center at the University of
616 Oklahoma (US) provided support for A.J.C. A grant from the Spanish National Institute for
617 Agriculture and Food Research and Technology (INIA), which is co-funded by the Social European
618 Fund provided support for M.G.L.

619

620 **References**

- 621 Abram, N. K., E. Meijaard, M. Ancrenaz, R. K. Runting, J. A. Wells, D. Gaveau, A. Pellier, and K.
622 Mengersen. 2014. Spatially explicit perceptions of ecosystem services and land cover change in
623 forested regions of Borneo. *Ecosystem Services* 7:116-127.
624 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2013.11.004>
- 625 Aguilar, M. A., Vallario, A., Aguilar, F. J., García Lorca, A., and C. Parente. 2015. Object-Based
626 Greenhouse Horticultural Crop Identification from Multi-Temporal Satellite Imagery: A Case Study
627 in Almeria, Spain. *Remote Sensing* 7:7378-7401. <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/rs70607378>
- 628 Allendorf, T. D. 2007. Residents' attitudes toward three protected areas in southwestern Nepal.
629 *Biodiversity and Conservation* 16:2087–2102. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s10531-006-9092-z>
- 630 Altieri, M. A., and V. M. Toledo. 2005. Natural Resource Management among Small-scale Farmers
631 in Semi-arid Lands: Building on Traditional Knowledge and Agroecology. *Annals of Arid Zone*
632 44:365-3
- 633 Antrop, M. 2004. Landscape change and the urbanization process in Europe. *Landscape and Urban*
634 *Planning* 67:9–26. [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0169-2046\(03\)00026-4](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0169-2046(03)00026-4)
- 635 Armas, C., J. D. Miranda, F. M. Padilla, and F. I. Pugnaire. 2011. Special issue: the Iberian
636 Southeast. *Journal of Arid Environments* 75:1241–1243.
637 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jaridenv.2011.08.002>
- 638 Armsworth, P. R., K. M. A. Chan, G. C. Daily, P. R. Erhlich, C. Kremen, T. H. Ricketts, and M. A.
639 Sanjayan. 2007. Ecosystem-service science and the way forward for conservation. *Conservation*
640 *Biology* 21:1383–1384. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/j.1523-1739.2007.00821.x>
- 641 Arnaez, J., T. Lasanta, M. P. Errea, and L. Ortigosa. 2011. Land abandonment, landscape evolution,
642 and soil erosion in a Spanish Mediterranean mountain region: the case of Camero Viejo. *Land*
643 *degradation & development*. 22:537–550. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/ldr.1032>
- 644 Aznar-Sánchez, J. A., E. Galdeano-Gómez, and J. C. Pérez-Mesa. 2011. Intensive Horticulture in
645 Almería (Spain): A Counterpoint to Current European Rural Policy Strategies. *Journal of Agrarian*
646 *Change* 11:241–261. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/j.1471-0366.2011.00301.x>

647 Bennet, E. M., G. D. Peterson, and L. J. Gordon. 2009. Understanding relationships among multiple
648 ecosystem services. *Ecology Letters* 12:1394–1404. [http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/j.1461-](http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/j.1461-0248.2009.01387.x)
649 0248.2009.01387.x

650 Blondel, J., J. Aronson, J.-Y. Bodiou, and G. Boeuf. 2010. *The Mediterranean Region Biological*
651 *Diversity in Space and Time*. Oxford: Oxford University Press

652 Butler, J. R. A., G. Y. Wong, D. J. Metcalfe, M. Honzák, P. L. Pert, N. Rao, M. E. van Grieken, T.
653 Lawson, C. Bruce, F. J. Kroon, and J. E. Brodie. 2011. An analysis of trade-offs between multiple
654 ecosystem services and stakeholders linked to land use and water quality management in the Great
655 Barrier Reef, Australia. *Agriculture, Ecosystems and Environment* 180:176-191.
656 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2011.08.017>

657 CAMP Levante de Almería (Coastal Areas Management Project). 2013. Ministerio de Agricultura,
658 Alimentación y Medio Ambiente, Consejería de Agricultura, Pesca y Medio Ambiente de la Junta
659 de Andalucía y Centro de Actividad Regional del Programa de Actividades Prioritarias. Plan de
660 Acción del Mediterráneo del Programa de Naciones Unidas para el Medio Ambiente. NIPO 280-13-
661 022-5

662 Carpenter, S. R., R. DeFries, T. Dietz, H. A. Mooney, S. Polasky, W. V. Reid, and R. J. Scholes.
663 2006. Millennium Ecosystem Assessment: Research Needs. *Science* 314:257-258.
664 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1126/science.1131946>

665 Carpenter, S. R., H. A. Mooney, J. Agard, D. Capistrano, R. S. DeFries, S. Díaz, T. Dietz, A. K.
666 Duraiappah, A. Oteng-Yeboah, H. M. Pereira, C. Perrings, W. V. Reid, J. Sarukhan, R. J. Scholes
667 and A. Whyte. 2009. Science for managing ecosystem services: Beyond the Millennium Ecosystem
668 Assessment. *PNAS* 3:106 no. 5 1305-1312. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0808772106>

669 Castro, A. J., B. Martín-López, M. García-Llorente, P. A. Aguilera, E. López, and J. Cabello. 2011.
670 Social preferences regarding the delivery of ecosystem services in a semiarid Mediterranean region.
671 *Journal of Arid Environment* 75:1201–1208. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jaridenv.2011.05.013>

672 Castro, A. J., P. H. Verburg, B. Martín-López, M. García-Llorente, J. Cabello, C. C. Vaughn, and E.
673 López. 2014. Ecosystem service trade-offs from supply to social demand: A landscape-scale spatial
674 analysis. *Landscape and Urban Planning* 132:102–110.
675 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.landurbplan.2014.08.009>

676 Castro, A. J., B. Martín-López, E. López, T. Plieninger, D. Alcaraz-Segura, C. C. Vaughn, and J.
677 Cabello. 2015. Do protected areas networks ensure the supply of ecosystem services? Spatial
678 patterns of two nature reserve systems in semi-arid Spain. *Applied Geography* 60:1-9.
679 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.apgeog.2015.02.012>

680 Castro, A. J., C. C. Vaughn, J. P. Julian, and M. García-Llorente. 2016. Social Demand for
681 Ecosystem Services and Implications for Watershed Management. *Journal of the American Water*
682 *Resources Association (JAWRA)* 52(1): 209-221. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/1752-1688.12379>

683 Costanza, R., R. de Groot, P. Sutton, S. van der Ploeg, S. J. Anderson, I. Kubiszewski, S. Farber,
684 and R. K. Turner. 2014. Changes in the global value of ecosystem services. *Global Environmental*
685 *Change* 26:152–158. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2014.04.002>

686 Dale, V. H., and S. Polasky. 2007. Measures of the effects of agricultural practices on ecosystem
687 services. *Ecological Economics* 64:286–296. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2007.05.009>

688 Davies, K. K., K. T. Fisher, M. E. Dickson, S. E. Thrush, R. Le Heron. 2015. Improving ecosystem
689 service frameworks to address wicked problems. *Ecology & Society* 20(2):37.
690 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5751/ES-07581-200237>

691 Di Iacovo, F., R. Moruzzo, C. Rossignoli, and P. Scarpellini. 2014. Transition management and
692 social innovation in rural areas: lessons from social farming. *Journal of Agricultural Education and*
693 *Extension* 20:327-347. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/1389224X.2014.887761>

694 Dupras, J., L. Parcerisas, and J. Brenner. 2015. Using ecosystem services valuation to measure the
695 economic impacts of land-use changes on the Spanish Mediterranean coast (El Maresme, 1850–
696 2010). *Regional Environmental Change* <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s10113-015-0847-5>

697 EEA - European Environmental Agency. 2010. *Europe's Ecological Backbone: Recognizing the*
698 *True Value of Our Mountains*. Copenhagen.

699 European Commission, 2015. Factsheet on 2014-2020 National Rural Development Programme for
700 Spain. Retrieved from: [http://ec.europa.eu/agriculture/rural-development-2014-2020/country-](http://ec.europa.eu/agriculture/rural-development-2014-2020/country-files/es/factsheet_en.pdf)
701 [files/es/factsheet_en.pdf](http://ec.europa.eu/agriculture/rural-development-2014-2020/country-files/es/factsheet_en.pdf)

702 Felipe-Lucia, M-R., F. A. Comín, and E. M. Bennett. 2014. Interactions among ecosystem services
703 across land uses in a floodplain agroecosystem. *Ecology & Society* 19(1):20.
704 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5751/ES-06249-190120>

705 Fischer, J., T. Hartel, and T. Kuemmerle. 2012. Conservation policy in traditional farming
706 landscapes. *Conservation Letters* 5:167-175. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/j.1755-263X.2012.00227.x>

707 Foley, J. A., R. Defries, G. P. Asner, C. Barford, G. Bonan, S. R. Carpenter, F. S. Chapin, M. T.
708 Coe, G. C. Daily, H. K. Gibbs, J. H. Helkowski, T. Holloway, E. A. Howard, C. J. Kucharic, C.
709 Monfreda, J. A. Patz, I. C. Prentice, N. Ramankutty, and P. K. Snyder. 2005. Global consequences
710 of land use. *Science* 309:570-574. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1126/science.1111772>

711 Fu, B., L. Zhang, Z. Xu, Y. Zhao, Y. Wei, and D. Skinner. 2015. Ecosystem services in changing
712 land use. *Journal of Soils and Sediments* 15:833-843. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s11368-015-1082-x>

713 García-Latorre, J., J. García-Latorre, and A. Sánchez-Picón. 2001. ‘Dealing with Aridity: Socio-
714 economic Structures and Environmental Changes in an Arid Mediterranean Region’. *Land Use*
715 *Policy* 18:53–64. [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0264-8377\(00\)00045-4](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0264-8377(00)00045-4)

716 García-Llorente, M., B. Martín-López, P. A. L. D. Nunes, A. J. Castro, and C. Montes. 2012a. A
717 choice experiment study for land use scenarios in semi-arid watershed environments. *Journal of*
718 *Arid Environments* 87:219–230. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jaridenv.2012.07.015>

719 García-Llorente, M., B. Martín-López, I. Iniesta-Arandia, C. A. López-Santiago, P. A. Aguilera,
720 and C. Montes. 2012b. The role of multi-functionality in social preferences toward semi-arid rural
721 landscapes: an ecosystem service approach. *Environmental Science & Policy* 19–20:136–146.
722 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2012.01.006>

723 García-Llorente, M., I. Iniesta-Arandia, B. A. Willaarts, P. A. Harrison, P. Berry, M. M. Bayo, A. J.
724 Castro, C. Montes, and B. Martín-López. 2015. Biophysical and sociocultural factors underlying
725 spatial trade-offs of ecosystem services in semiarid watersheds. *Ecology and Society* 20(3):39.
726 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5751/ES-07785-200339>

727 García-Quesada, M., F. Jiménez, and M. Villoria. 2015. Can’t control/won’t control: opportunities
728 and deterrents for local urban corruption in Lanzarote. *Crime, Law and Social Change* 63:1-20.
729 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s10611-014-9549-z>

730 Garrido Cumbreira, M., and E. López Lara. 2010. Consecuencias del turismo de masas en el litoral
731 de Andalucía (España). *Caderno Virtual de Turismo* 10:125-135

732 Gonzalez, L., and F. Ortega. 2009. Immigration and Housing Booms: Evidence from Spain.
733 *Discussion Paper Series IZA DP No. 4333*

734 Gordon, L. J., C. M. Finlayson, and M. Falkenmark. 2010. Managing water in agriculture for food
735 production and other ecosystem services. *Agricultural Water Management* 97:512-519.
736 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.agwat.2009.03.017>

737 Gulinck, H., M. Múgica, J. V. De Lucio, and J. A. Atauri. 2001. A framework for comparative
738 landscape analysis and evaluation based on land cover data, with an application in the Madrid
739 region (Spain). *Landscape and Urban Planning* 55:257-270. [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0169-](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0169-2046(01)00159-1)
740 [2046\(01\)00159-1](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0169-2046(01)00159-1)

741 Hewitt, R., and F. Escobar. 2011. The territorial dynamics of fast-growing regions: Unsustainable
742 land use change and future policy challenges in Madrid, Spain. *Applied Geography* 31:650-667

743 Hose, T. A. 2007. Geotourism in Almeria Province, southeast Spain. *TOURISM Preliminary*
744 *communication* 55:259-276 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.apgeog.2010.11.002>

745 INE. 2011. National Statistics Institute. Spanish Statistical Office. <http://www.ine.es>

746 Iniesta-Arandia, I., D. García del Amo, A. P. García-Nieto, C. Piñeiro, C. Montes, and B. Martín-
747 López. 2015. Factors influencing local ecological knowledge maintenance in Mediterranean
748 watersheds: Insights for environmental policies. *AMBIO* 44:285-296.
749 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s13280-014-0556-1>

750 Jiménez, F., M. García-Quesada, and M. Villoria. 2014. Integrity Systems, Values, and
751 Expectations: Explaining Differences in the Extent of Corruption in Three Spanish Local
752 Governments. *International Journal of Public Administration* 37:67-82.
753 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/01900692.2013.836666>

754 Keenleyside, C, G. Beaufoy, G. Tucker, and G. Jones. 2014. High Nature Value farming throughout
755 EU-27 and its financial support under the CAP. Report Prepared for DG Environment, Contract No
756 ENV B.1/ETU/2012/0035, Institute for European Environmental Policy, London

757 Kuriyan, R. 2002. Linking local perceptions of elephants and conservation: Samburu pastoralists in
758 Northern Kenya. *Society & Natural Resources* 15:949-957.
759 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/08941920290107675>

760 Laurans, Y., A. Rankovic, R. Billé, R. Pirard, and L. Mermet. 2013. Use of ecosystem services
761 economic valuation for decision making: Questioning a literature blindspot. *Journal of*
762 *Environmental Management* 119:208-219. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2013.01.008>

763 Law 2/1989, de 18 de Julio, de Inventario de espacios naturales protegidos de Andalucía. BOJA nº
764 60 de 27/7/1989

765 Law 3/1999, de 11 de Enero, creación del Parque Nacional de Sierra Nevada. BOE-A-1999-782

766 Law 7/2002, de 17 de Diciembre, de Ordenación Urbanística de Andalucía. BOJA nº 154 de
767 31/12/2002

768 Law 42/2007, de 13 de Diciembre, del Patrimonio Natural y de la Biodiversidad. BOE 299:51275-
769 51327

770 Law 45/2007, de 13 de Diciembre, del Patrimonio Natural y de la Biodiversidad. BOE 299:51339-
771 51349

772 Lawler, J. J., D. J. Lewis, E. Nelson, A. J. Plantinga, S. Polasky, J. C. Withey, D. P. Helmers, S.
773 Martinuzzi, D. Pennington, and V. C. Radeloff. 2014. Projected land-use change impacts on
774 ecosystem services in the United States. *PNAS* 111:7492-7497.
775 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1405557111>

776 Lázaro, R., F. S. Rodrigo, L. Gutiérrez, F. Domingo, and J. Puigdefábregas. 2001. Analysis of a 30-
777 year rainfall record (1967-1997) in semi-arid SE Spain for implications on vegetation. *Journal of*
778 *Arid Environments* 48:373-395. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1006/jare.2000.0755>

779 Legislative decree 314/1987, de 23 de diciembre, declaración del Parque Natural de Cabo de Gata-
780 Níjar. BOJA nº 6 de 26/1/1988

781 López-Rodríguez, M. D., A. J. Castro, H. Castro, S. Jorreto, and J. Cabello. 2015. Science–policy
782 interface for addressing environmental problems in arid Spain. *Environmental Science and Policy*
783 50:1-14. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2015.01.013>

784 Martín-García, J. 2007. Transformaciones y cambios recientes de uso del suelo en el litoral del
785 levante almeriense. *Geografía y ordenación del territorio [go] - Paralelo 37º - Estudios*
786 *geográficos, Antigua colección: Paralelo 37º* 19:123. ISBN: 0210-3796

787 Martín-López, B., I. Iniesta-Arandia, M. García-Llorente, I. Palomo, I. Casado-Arzuaga, D. García
788 Del Amo, E. Gómez-Baggethun, E. Oteros-Rozas, I. Palacios-Agundez, B. Willaarts, J. A.
789 González, F. Santos-Martín, M. Onaindia, C. López-Santiago, and C. Montes. 2012. Uncovering

790 ecosystem services bundles through social preferences. *PLoS One* 7,1-11e38970.
791 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0038970>

792 Martinez-Harms, M. J., B. A. Bryan, P. Balvanera, E. A. Law, J. R. Rhodes, H. P. Possingham, and
793 K. A. Wilson. 2015. Making decisions for managing ecosystem services. *Biological*
794 *Conservation*.184:229–238. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2015.01.024>

795 McShane, T. O., P. D. Hirsch, T. C. Trung, A. N. Songorwa, A. Kinzig, B. Monteferri,
796 D. Mutekanga, H. Van Thang, J. L. Dammert, M. Pulgar-Vidal, M. Welch-Devine,
797 J. P. Brosius, P. Coppolillo, and S. O'Connor. 2011. Hard choices: making trade-offs between
798 biodiversity conservation and human well-being. *Biological Conservation* 144:966–972.
799 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2010.04.038>

800 Millennium Ecosystem Assessment (MA). 2005. Millennium ecosystem assessment synthesis
801 report. Island Press, Washington, D.C., USA

802 Mota, J. F., J. Peñas, H. Castro, and J. Cabello. 1996. Agricultural development vs biodiversity
803 conservation: the Mediterranean semiarid vegetation in El Ejido (Almería, southeastern Spain).
804 *Biodiversity and Conservation* 5:1597-1617. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/BF00052118>

805 Mouchet, M. A., P. Lamarque, B. Martín-López, E. Crouzat, P. Gos, C. Byczek, and S. Lavorel.
806 2014. An interdisciplinary methodological guide for quantifying associations between ecosystem
807 services. *Global Environmental Change* 28:298–308.
808 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2014.07.012>

809 Muñoz, P., A. Antón, M. Nuñez, A. Vijay, J. Ariño, X. Castells, J. Montero, and J. Rieradevall.
810 2008. Comparing the environmental impacts of greenhouse versus open-field tomato production in
811 the Mediterranean region. ISHS. Acta Horticulturae (Ed.), International Conference on Sustainable
812 Greenhouse Systems – GREENSYS 2007. 4–6 October 2008, Naples, Italy

813 Muñoz-Flores, J. C. 2011. El Plan de Desarrollo Sostenible de Cabo de Gata-Níjar: ¿Una
814 oportunidad perdida? Editorial: Universidad de Almería. ISBN: 978-84-8240-192-8. 81pp.

815 Muñoz-Rojas, M., D. De la Rosa, L. M. Zavala, A. Jordán, and M. Anaya-Romero. 2011. Changes
816 in land cover and vegetation carbon stocks in Andalusia, Southern Spain (1956-2007). *Science of*
817 *Total Environment* 409:2796-2806. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2011.04.009>

- 818 Navarro, L. M., and H. M. Pereira. 2012. Rewilding Abandoned Landscapes in Europe. *Ecosystems*
819 15:900–912. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s10021-012-9558-7>
- 820 Nelson, E., H. Sander, P. Hawthorne, M. Conte, D. Ennaanay, S. Wolny, S. Manson, and S.
821 Polasky. 2010. Projecting Global Land-Use Change and Its Effect on Ecosystem Service Provision
822 and Biodiversity with Simple Models. *PLoS ONE* 5(12) e14327.
823 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0014327>
- 824 Palomo, I., B. Martín-López, M. Potschin, R. Haines-Young, and C. Montes. 2013. National Parks,
825 buffer zones and surrounding lands: Mapping ecosystem service flows. *Ecosystem services* 4:104-
826 116. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2012.09.001>
- 827 Palomo, I., C. Montes, B. Martín-López, J. A. González, M. García-Llorente, P. Alcorlo, and M. R.
828 García Mora. 2014a. Incorporating the Social–Ecological Approach in Protected Areas in the
829 Anthropocene. *BioScience* 64:181-191. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1093/biosci/bit033>
- 830 Palomo, I., B. Martín-López, P. Alcorlo, and C. Montes. 2014b. Limitations of Protected Areas
831 Zoning in Mediterranean Cultural Landscapes Under the Ecosystem Services Approach.
832 *Ecosystems* 17:1202-1215. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s10021-014-9788-y>
- 833 Palutikof, J. P., M. Conte, J. Casimiro Mendes, C. M. Goodess, and F. Espiritu Santo. 1996.
834 Climate and Climatic Change. In: Brandt, C.J. & Thornes J.B. (Eds.), *Mediterranean Desertification*
835 *and Land Use*, pp. 43–86. Chichester: John Wiley & Sons. 547 pp.
- 836 Pardo de Santayana, M., R. Morales, L. Aceituno-Mata, and M. Molina (eds.). 2014. Inventario
837 español de los conocimientos tradicionales relativos a la biodiversidad. Ministerio de Agricultura,
838 Alimentación y Medio Ambiente. Madrid. 411 pp.
- 839 Pereira, E., C. Queiroz, H. M. Pereira, and L. Vicente. 2005. Ecosystem Services and Human Well-
840 Being: a Participatory Study in a Mountain Community in Portugal. *Ecology and Society* 10(2):14
- 841 Pereira, H. M., P. W. Leadley, V. Proença, R. Alkemade, J. P. W. Scharlemann, J. F. Fernandez-
842 Manjarrés, M. B. Araújo, P. Balvanera, R. Biggs, W. W. L. Cheung, L. Chini, H. D. Cooper, E. L.
843 Gilman, S. Guénette, G. C. Hurtt, H. P. Huntington, G. M. Mace, T. Oberdorff, C. Revenga, P.
844 Rodrigues, R. J. Scholes, U. R. Sumaila, and M. Walpole. 2010. Scenarios for Global Biodiversity
845 in the 21st Century. *Science* 330:1496-1501. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1126/science.1196624>

846 Pereira, H. M., L. M. Navarro, and I. Santos Martins. 2012. Global Biodiversity Change: The Bad,
847 the Good, and the Unknown. *Annual Review of Environment and Resources* 37:25–50.
848 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1146/annurev-environ-042911-093511>

849 Power, A. G. 2010. Ecosystem services and agriculture: tradeoffs and synergies. *Philosophical*
850 *Transactions of the Royal Society B* 365:2959-2971. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1098/rstb.2010.0143>

851 Pyke, C. R. 2007. The implications of global priorities for biodiversity and ecosystem services
852 associated with protected areas. *Ecology and Society* 12(1):4

853 Queiroz, C., M. Meacham, K. Richter, A. V. Norström, E. Andersson, J. Norberg, and G. Peterson.
854 2015. Mapping bundles of ecosystem services reveals distinct types of multifunctionality within a
855 Swedish landscape. *AMBIO* 44:89-101. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s13280-014-0601-0>

856 Quintas-Soriano, C., A. J. Castro, M. García-Llorente, J. Cabello, and H. Castro. 2014. From supply
857 to social demand: a landscape-scale analysis of the water regulation service. *Landscape Ecology*
858 29:1069-1082. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s10980-014-0032-0>

859 REDIAM. The Environmental Information Network of Andalusia. 2007. The Department of
860 Environment of the Andalusian government. Andalusia vegetation cover and land-use maps.
861 <http://www.juntadeandalucia.es/medioambiente/site/rediam>

862 Reyers, B., P. J. O’Farrell, R. M. Cowling, B. N. Egoh, D. C. Le Maitre and J. H. J. Vlok. 2009.
863 Ecosystem services, land-cover change, and stakeholders: finding a sustainable foothold for a
864 semiarid biodiversity hotspot. *Ecology and Society* 14(1):38

865 Rodríguez, J. P., T. D. Beard Jr., E. M. Bennett, G. S. Cumming, S. Cork, J. Agard, A. P. Dobson,
866 and G. D. Peterson. 2006. Trade-offs across space, time, and ecosystem services. *Ecology and*
867 *Society* 11(1):28

868 Romero, J., F. Jiménez, and M. Villoria. 2012. (Un)sustainable territories: causes of the speculative
869 bubble in Spain (1996–2010) and its territorial, environmental, and sociopolitical consequences.
870 *Environment and Planning C: Government and Policy* 30:467–486.
871 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1068/c11193r>

872 Royal legislative decree 24/1941. Instituto Nacional de Colonización. Decreto de 24/06/41 por el
873 que se declara de alto interés nacional la colonización de la zona denominada Campo de Dalías, en
874 la provincia de Almería. BOE (7/07/41), nº 4052

875 Ruiz-Benito, P., J. A. Cuevas, R. Bravo de la Parra, F. Prieto, J. M. García del Barrio, and M. A.
876 Zavala. 2010. Land use change in a Mediterranean metropolitan region and its periphery:
877 assessment of conservation policies through CORINE Land Cover data and Markov models. *Forest*
878 *Systems* 19:315-328. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5424/fs/2010193-8604>

879 Sala, O. E., F. S. Chapin III, J. J. Armesto, E. Berlow, J. Bloomfield, R. Dirzo, E. Huber-Sanwald,
880 L. F. Huenneke, R. B. Jackson, A. Kinzig, R. Leemans, D. M. Lodge, H. A. Mooney, M.
881 Oesterheld, N. L. Poff, M. T. Sykes, B. H. Walker, M. Walker, and D. H. Wall. 2000. Global
882 Biodiversity Scenarios for the Year 2100. *Science* 287:1770-1774.
883 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1126/science.287.5459.1770>

884 Sánchez-Picón, A., J. A. Aznar-Sánchez, and J. García-Latorre. 2011. Economic cycles and
885 environmental crisis in arid southeastern Spain. A historical perspective. *Journal of Arid*
886 *Environments* 75:1360-1367. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jaridenv.2010.12.014>

887 Schouten, M. H., C. M. van der Heide, W. J. M. Heijman, and P. F. M. Opdam. 2012. A resilience-
888 based policy evaluation framework: Application to European rural development policies.
889 *Ecological Economics* 81:165–175. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2012.07.004>

890 Schröter, D., W. Cramer, R. Leemans, I. C. Prentice, M. B. Araújo, N. W. Arnell, A. Bondeau, H.
891 Bugmann, T. R. Carter, C. A. Gracia, A. C. de la Vega-Leinert, M. Erhard, F. Ewert, M.
892 Glendining, J. I. House, S. Kankaanpää, R. J. T. Klein, S. Lavorel, M. Lindner, M. J. Metzger, J.
893 Meyer, T. D. Mitchell, I. Reginster, M. Rounsevell, S. Sabaté, S. Sitch, B. Smith, J. Smith, P.
894 Smith, M. T. Sykes, K. Thonicke, W. Thuiller, G. Tuck, S. Zaehle, and B. Zierl. 2005. Ecosystem
895 Service Supply and Vulnerability to Global Change in Europe. *Science* 310:1333-1337.
896 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1126/science.1115233>

897 Secretariat of the Convention on Biological Diversity. (2010). Strategic Plan for Biodiversity
898 2011e2020 and the Aichi Targets. “Living in harmony with nature”. Quebec: Canada: CBD, UNEP

899 Sherren, K., and C. Verstraten. 2013. What can photo-elicitation tell us about how maritime farmers
900 perceive wetlands as climate change? *Wetlands* 33:65–81. [http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s13157-012-](http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s13157-012-0352-2)
901 [0352-2](http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s13157-012-0352-2)

902 Spanish National Ecosystem Assessment. 2014. Ecosystems and biodiversity for human wellbeing.
903 Synthesis of the key findings. Biodiversity Foundation of the Spanish Ministry of Agriculture, Food

904 and Environment. Madrid, Spain 90 pp.

905 Stellmes, M., A. Röder, T. Udelhoven, and J. Hill. 2013. Mapping syndromes of land change in
906 Spain with remote sensing time series, demographic and climatic data. *Land Use Policy* 30:685–
907 702. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2012.05.007>

908 Subirós, V. J., R. Rodríguez-Carreras, D. Varga1, A. Ribas, X. Úbeda, F. Asperó, A. Llausàs, and
909 L. Outeiro. 2015. Stakeholder perceptions of landscape changes in the Mediterranean mountains of
910 the northeastern Iberian Peninsula. *Land Degradation & Development*
911 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/ldr.2337>

912 United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP). 2005. One Planet, Many People: Atlas of Our
913 Changing Environment. Nairobi: UNEP

914 Vidal-Legaz, B., J. Martínez-Fernández, A. Sánchez Picón, and F. I. Pugnaire. 2013. Trade-offs
915 between maintenance of ecosystem services and socio-economic development in rural mountainous
916 communities in southern Spain: A dynamic simulation approach. *Journal of Environmental*
917 *Management* 131:280-297. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2013.09.036>

918 Villoria, M., F. Jiménez, and A. Revuelta. 2014. Corruption perception and collective action: The
919 case of Spain. En J. Mendilow and I. Peleg (eds.), *Corruption in the Contemporary World: Theory,*
920 *Practice and Hotspots*. Maryland: Lexington Books, pp. 197-222

921 Vivas-Puig, F. 2007. Ley de costas e invernaderos en el poniente almeriense. *Paralelo 37. Revista*
922 *de Estudios Geográficos* 19:185-208

923 Watson, J. E. M., N. Dudley, D. B. Segan, and M. Hockin. 2014. The performance and potential of
924 protected areas *Nature* 515:67–73. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1038/nature13947>

925 Weissteiner, C. J., M. Boschetti, K. Böttcher, P. Carrara, G. Bordogna, and P. A. Brivio. 2011.
926 Spatial explicit assessment of rural land abandonment in the Mediterranean area. *Global and*
927 *Planetary change* 79:20-36. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.gloplacha.2011.07.009>

928 Wolosin, R. T. 2008. "El Milagro De Almeria, España: A Political Ecology of Landscape Change
929 and Greenhouse Agriculture". Theses, Dissertations, Professional Papers. Paper 366

930 Zalidis, G., S. Stamatiadis, V. Takavakoglou, K. Eskridge, and N. Misopolinos. 2002. Impacts of
931 agricultural practices on soil and water quality in the Mediterranean region and proposed

932 assessment methodology. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment* 88:137–146.

933 [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0167-8809\(01\)00249-3](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0167-8809(01)00249-3)

934

935 **Figure captions**

936 Figure 1. Location of the study area, spatial distribution of the land use-land cover (LULC) types,
937 and sampling points.

938 Figure 2. Examples of the main land use-land cover (LULC) changes that occurred in the study
939 area. (A) *El Poniente* area in 1970, and (B) the conversion of *El Poniente* into greenhouses in 2006.
940 (C) *El Algarrobico* hotel within the *Cabo de Gata Natural Park*. (D) *Punta Entinas-Sabinar*
941 *Natural Reserve* surrounded by the intensively managed landscape of Almeria, Spain.

942 Figure 3. Perceived impacts of land use-land cover (LULC) types on ecosystem services. The grey
943 area in the spider diagram represents the negative impact, and the white area represents the positive
944 impact.

945 Figure 4. (A) Social importance and (B) trend of ecosystem services (increase, stable or decrease).

946 Figure 5. Links between the perceived impacts of ecosystem services, the indirect drivers of change
947 and the components of human well-being for each LULC type. Only the main impacts of the
948 ecosystem services and the main indirect drivers of change were included.

949

950
951

952

953

Greenhouse horticulture

Urban intensification

Rural abandonment

Protected areas

954

955

959

960

961

962 Table 1. Arguments for and against each land use-land cover (LULC) type, number of respondents
 963 mentioning each argument (expressed as the percentage of the total respondents), related direct
 964 drivers (land use change, climatic change, pollution, invasive alien species, biogeochemical cycles
 965 changes, and overexploitation) and indirect drivers (demographic, economic, sociopolitical, science
 966 and technology, cultural and gender drivers), and components of human well-being (basic material
 967 for a good life, health, security, good social relations, and freedom of choice and action).

Arguments	Frequency (%)	Direct drivers (predominant)	Indirect drivers (predominant)	Human well-being (predominant)
Greenhouse horticulture				
In favor (69.15%)				
Promotion of employment and lifestyle	42.09		Economic	Basic material for a good life; Security
Creation of economic development	28.06		Economic	Basic material for a good life; Security
Increasing farming productivity	12.23		Economic	Basic material for a good life; Security
Obtaining products out of season	9.71		Science and technology	Basic material for a good life
Against (65.67%)				
Pollution (burning agricultural plastics and chemical contamination)	30.30	Pollution		Health
Aesthetic impact	16.21	Land-use change		
Ecological impact	9.85	Land-use change		Health; Security
Excessive land occupation	6.82	Land-use change		
Social inequality and worker overexploitation	6.06		Demographic; Sociopolitical; Cultural	Freedom of choice and action
Soil erosion	4.55	Climatic change		Security
Urban intensification				
In favor (55.22%)				
Promotion of employment	42.79		Economic	Security
Creation of housing	17.57		Economic; Demographic	Basic material for a good life; Security
Creation of economic development	13.96		Economic	Basic material for a good life; Security
Promotion of human well-being	9.46		All	All
Increasing tourism	6.31		Economic; Cultural	Good social relations; Freedom of choice and action
Increasing population	5.41		Economic; Demographic	
Against (74.88%)				
Uncontrolled urban expansion and housing oversupply	45.85	Land-use change	Demographic; Socio-political; Economic	Security
Corruption and speculation	20.93		Socio-political; Economic	Basic material for a good life
Ecological impact	11.30	Land-use change	Demographic; Economic; Socio-political	Health; Security
Aesthetic impact	4.98	Land-use change	Demographic; Economic; Socio-political	
Overpriced housing	4.65		Economic	Security
Soil loss	3.32	Land-use change	Demographic; Economic; Socio-political	Health; Security
Rural abandonment				
In favor (24.88%)				

Search for job opportunities	34.00		Economic; Cultural	Security; Freedom of choice and action
Life quality improvement	27.00		Economic; Demographic	Security; Freedom of choice and action
Restoration of natural environment	13.00			Health
Against (35.91%)				
Loss of local identity and local ecological knowledge	41.32		Cultural; Science and technology	Good social relationships
Rural depopulation	16.17	Land-use change	Demographic; Economic; Cultural	Good social relationships; Security
Crop abandonment	11.98	Land-use change	Economic; Cultural	Basic material for a good life; Health
<hr/>				
Protected areas				
In favor (71.64%)				
Environment conservation and biodiversity protection	64.93		Socio-political; Cultural	Basic material for a good life; Health
Promotion of human well-being and health	9.38		All	All
Increasing tourism	10.75		Economic; Cultural	Good social relations; Freedom of choice and action
Against (31.84%)				
Excessive legislation and banning	35.94	Land-use change	Socio-political	Freedom of choice and action
Limitation of human development	21.88	Land-use change	Socio-political; Economic	All

968

969

970 Table 2. Kruskal–Wallis test and Dunn groups to compare the impact of land use-land cover
 971 (LULC) on ecosystem services. Letters in parentheses represent statistically different groups as
 972 identified by the Dunn test. In bold the most remarkable results.

	Traditional agriculture	Intensive agriculture	Air quality	Climate regulation	Water regulation	Erosion control	Tourism	Local identity
Greenhouse horticulture	- (B)	+ (C)	- (A)	- (A)	- (A)	- (B)	- (A)	+ (B)
Urban intensification	- (B)	+ (B)	- (A)	- (B)	- (A)	- (A)	+ (C)	+ (C)
Rural abandonment	- (A)	+ (B)	+ (B)	+ (C)	- (B)	- (B)	- (A)	- (A)
Protected areas	- (B)	- (A)	+ (C)	+ (D)	+ (C)	+ (C)	+ (B)	+ (BC)
Kruskal-Wallis test	112.55***	684.23***	389.54***	278.66***	150.09***	242.60***	410.47***	315.65***

973 *** Statistical significance = 1 %.

974

975 Table 3. Policies regulation at European and Spanish levels and the contributions of this study.

Policy target	Policy Regulation at European level	Spanish Policy Regulation	Contributions of this study
Biodiversity conservation	Strategic Plan for Biodiversity 2011–2020 and the Aichi Targets	Natural Heritage and Biodiversity Spanish Strategic Program (Law 42/2007 on Natural Heritage and Biodiversity)	
	TARGET 2: To maintain and enhance ecosystems and their services	GOAL 1: To obtain the best knowledge for the conservation and sustainable use of biodiversity and ecosystem services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To improve the knowledge of linkages between ecosystem services and land uses • To inform environmental policies • To highlight the social recognition of the local ecological knowledge and local identity in rural areas which provide the evidence of social support needed to create the Spanish Inventory of Traditional Knowledge¹ • To prevent degradation of rural areas characterized by multifunctional agriculture by enhancing their ecological values and designing high nature value farming areas
	TARGET 3: To increase the contribution of agriculture and forestry to maintaining and enhancing biodiversity	GOAL 5: To promote the social participation in the biodiversity conservation and promote their awareness and commitment	
Rural development	EU's Rural Development Policy	National Rural Development Program for Spain (Law 45/2007 for Sustainable Rural Development)	
	PRIORITY 4: Restoring, preserving and enhancing ecosystems related to agriculture and forestry	PRIORITY 4A: To restore, preserve and enhance biodiversity, agricultural systems of high natural value and the state of European landscapes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To improve existing methods to conduct socio-cultural assessment of services in arid systems • To identify public arguments to establish high nature value farming areas which preserve multiple ecosystem services in rural areas • To facilitate the baseline information for a later participatory process to co-design public policies through a multi stakeholder governance focusing in local communities
	PRIORITY 6: Promoting social inclusion, poverty reduction and economic development in rural areas	PRIORITY 6B: To promote local development in rural areas: promoting the enhancement of natural and cultural heritage as a factor of sustainable development	

976
977